

Performance of Some Improved Estimators and Their Robust Versions Under Outliers: A Simulation Study

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Abstract:

This paper introduces enhanced estimators designed to address the issue of multicollinearity in multiple linear regression models. In addition to multicollinearity, the presence of outliers also presents a challenge in multiple linear regression analysis. To tackle these issues, this paper proposes several improved estimators, along with their robust counterparts, and compares their performance. The evaluation of these estimators is based on Monte Carlo simulations, under various outlier scenarios, including no outliers, one outlier, and two outliers. The mean squared error (MSE) is used as the performance criterion. The simulation results show that, when no outliers are present, the improved estimators outperform most of their robust versions. However, in the presence of one or two outliers, all robust versions of the improved estimators perform better than the conventional improved estimators.

Keywords:

Linear Regression; Mean Square Error; M-estimator; Multicollinearity; Outliers; Ridge Regression; Simulation Study.

1. Introduction

In multiple linear regression, the ordinary least squares (OLS) estimator is optimal under the assumption that explanatory variables are independent, and errors are normally distributed. However, in practical applications, explanatory variables are often highly correlated, leading to multicollinearity. Severe multicollinearity inflates the variances of regression coefficients, resulting in unstable estimates and unreliable inference. To overcome this problem, biased estimators such as ridge regression (Hoerl and Kennard, 1970) [4] and the Liu estimator (Liu, 1993)[8] have been developed, both of which introduce controlled bias to achieve lower mean squared error (MSE) compared to OLS.

While these estimators improve estimation under multicollinearity, they remain sensitive to outliers, which are common in real-world datasets, including epidemiological and biomedical studies. Outliers can distort coefficient estimates and degrade the performance of classical estimators. To address this issue, robust alternatives such as the robust ridge M-estimator (Silvapulle, 1991)[13] and the robust Liu estimator (Arslan and Billor, 2010) [2] have been proposed. These approaches combine the advantages of biased estimation with the protection of robust methods, yielding more reliable results under data contamination.

The purpose of this paper is to present the definitions and properties of these four estimators—ridge regression, Liu, robust ridge M, and robust Liu—and to highlight their performance under varying levels of multicollinearity and outlier contamination.

2. Statistical Methodology

In this section, we discuss the canonical form of linear regression model and different type of estimators, their bias, variance and MSE expressions.

2.1 Ridge Regression Estimator

To describe the ridge regression, consider following multiple linear regression model.

$$y = X\beta + \epsilon$$

where y is an $n \times 1$ vector of observations, β is an $p \times 1$ vector of unknown regression coefficients, X is an $n \times p$ observed matrix of the regressors and ϵ is an $n \times 1$ vector of random errors with mean 0 and covariance matrix $\sigma^2 I_n$ and I_n is an identity matrix of order n . The OLS estimator of β is obtained as

$$\hat{\beta}_{ols} = (X'X)^{-1}X'y$$

and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}$ is obtained as $Cov(\hat{\beta}) = \sigma^2(X'X)^{-1}$. It is easy to see that both $\hat{\beta}$ and $Cov(\hat{\beta})$ depend on characteristics of the matrix $X'X$. The standard regression model assumes that regressors are nearly independent. However, in many practical situations, one often finds that regressors are nearly dependent. In that case $X'X$ matrix becomes ill conditioned (i.e., $\det(X'X) \approx 0$). If $X'X$ is ill conditioned, then $\hat{\beta}$ is sensitive to several errors and consequently the meaningful statistical inference becomes very difficult for practitioners. To overcome this problem, Hoerl and Kennard (1970) suggested a small positive number to be added to diagonal elements of the matrix $X'X$. In fact, the ridge regression was obtained by augmenting the equation $0 = k^{\frac{1}{2}}\beta + \epsilon'$ and the resulting estimator is obtained as,

$$\hat{\beta}_k = (X'X + kI_p)^{-1}X'y = W\hat{\beta}, k \geq 0$$

where $W = (I_p + kC^{-1})$ and $C = X'X$. This is known as ridge regression estimator, where I_p is an identity matrix of order p . Since the quantity $[X'X + kI_p]$ in eq. (2) is always invertible, there always exist a unique solution for $\hat{\beta}(k)$. The ridge regression estimator is a biased estimator and for a positive value of k , it provides smaller MSE compared to the OLS estimator (Hoerl and Kennard, 1970). We observed that as, $k \rightarrow 0, \hat{\beta}(k) \rightarrow \hat{\beta}$ and as, $k \rightarrow \infty, \hat{\beta}(k) \rightarrow 0$.

The bias, variance matrix and MSE expressions of $\hat{\beta}(k)$ are respectively given as follows,

$$Bias = E(\hat{\beta}_k) - \beta = -kC_k^{-1}\beta, C_k = [C + kI_p]$$

$$V(\hat{\beta}(k)) = \sigma^2(WC^{-1}W')$$

$$MSE(\hat{\beta}_k) = \sigma^2 tr(WC^{-1}W') + k^2\beta'C_k^{-2}\beta.$$

The parameter k is known as “biased”, or “ridge” parameter and it must be estimated using real data. Most of recent efforts in multicollinearity and ridge regression estimators have concentrated on estimating value of k . We reviewed statistical methodology used to describe the estimation of k in the section follow.

2.1.1: Estimation of Ridge Parameter k

There are many methods to estimate the ridge parameter k . However, in this paper, we will consider 4 promising values of k from Mermi et al. (2021) and provided them below.

$$\hat{k}_1 = p\hat{\sigma} \quad \text{Lukman and Olatunji (2017) [10][12]}$$

$$\hat{k}_2 = \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\alpha}_{max}^2} \quad \text{Hoerl \& Kennard (1970) [4]}$$

$$\hat{k}_3 = \frac{p\hat{\sigma}^2}{\sum_i^p \lambda_i \hat{\alpha}_i^2} \quad \text{Lawless and Wang (1976) [7]}$$

$$k_4 = \max\left(\frac{\sigma^2}{\alpha_i^2}\right) \quad \text{Alkhamisi et al (2006) [1]}$$

2.2 Liu Estimator

To overcome the drawbacks of ridge estimator, which is the non-linear function of k , Liu (1993) [8] proposed a new biased estimator which is defined as,

$$\hat{\alpha}_L = (\Lambda + I)^{-1}(\Lambda + dI) \hat{\alpha}$$

where, $0 < d < 1$ is a shrinkage parameter. The advantage of $\hat{\alpha}_L$ over $\hat{\alpha}_k$ is that $\hat{\alpha}_L$ is a linear function of d . Therefore, it is easier to choose d over to choose k in the ridge parameter.

The bias, covariance, MSE and tr (MSE) expressions of Liu estimator are respectively given below,

$$Bias(\hat{\alpha}_L) = -(\Lambda + I)^{-1} (1 - d) \hat{\alpha}$$

$$Cov(\hat{\alpha}_L) = \sigma^2 (\Lambda + I)^{-1}(\Lambda + dI) \Lambda^{-1}(\Lambda + dI)(\Lambda + I)^{-1}$$

$$MSE(\hat{\alpha}_L) = Cov(\hat{\alpha}_L) + (bias(\hat{\alpha}_L))^2$$

$$= \sigma^2 (\Lambda + I)^{-1}(\Lambda + dI) \Lambda^{-1}(\Lambda + dI)(\Lambda + I)^{-1} + (d - 1)^2 (\Lambda + I)^{-1} \hat{\alpha} \hat{\alpha}' (\Lambda + I)^{-1}$$

$$tr(MSE(\hat{\alpha}_L)) = \sigma^2 \sum_{i=1}^p \frac{(\lambda_i + d)^2}{\lambda_i (\lambda_i + 1)^2} + \sum_{i=1}^p \frac{(d-1)^2 \alpha_i^2}{(\lambda_i + 1)^2}$$

we will consider the following d which is proposed by Lukman et al (2023) [9]

$$\hat{d} = \min\left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}_i^2}{\frac{1}{\lambda_i} + \hat{\alpha}_i^2}\right)$$

2.3 Robust Ridge M Estimator

When data has outliers, extreme observations, or does not follow a normal distribution, the alternative to the least squares method is Robust M Estimator. Silvapulle (1991) [13] proposed a robust ridge M-estimator (RM) which is defined as

$$\hat{\alpha}_{RRM} = (\Lambda + kI)^{-1}\Lambda \hat{\alpha}_M,$$

where $\hat{\alpha}_M$ is the robust M estimator defined by the solution of M-estimating equations $\sum_{i=1}^n \psi(\frac{u_i}{s}) = 0$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n \psi(\frac{u_i}{s})X_i = 0$, where, $u_i = Y_i - X_i'\hat{\alpha}_M$, ψ is the first derivative of some suitable chosen function and s is an estimator of scale for the errors also.

The bias, covariance and MSE and tr (MSE) expressions of RRM estimator are respectively:

$$Bias(\hat{\alpha}_{RRM}) = ((\Lambda + kI)^{-1}\Lambda - 1)\alpha$$

$$Cov(\hat{\alpha}_{RRM}) = \Omega((\Lambda + kI)^{-1}\Lambda'(\Lambda + kI)^{-1}), \text{ where } \Omega = cov(\hat{\alpha}_M)$$

$$MSE(\hat{\alpha}_{RRM}) = \Omega((\Lambda + kI)^{-1}\Lambda'(\Lambda + kI)^{-1} + k(\Lambda + k)^{-1}\alpha'\alpha(\Lambda + k)^{-1}k)$$

$$tr(MSE(\hat{\alpha}_{RRM})) = \sum_{i=1}^p \frac{\lambda_i^2}{(\lambda_i + k_i)^2} \Omega_{ii} + \sum_{i=1}^p \frac{k_i^2 \alpha_i^2}{(\lambda_i + k_i)^2},$$

where, Ω_{ii} is the diagonal elements of the matrix Ω .

We will consider the following k ,

$$\hat{k}_1 = p\sqrt{A^2},$$

where $A^2 = \frac{s^2 E\{\psi^2(\epsilon/s_0)\}}{(E\{\psi'(\epsilon/s_0)\})^2}$ with $s_0 = plim(s)$ and $\psi'(\epsilon/s_0) = \frac{d}{dt}\psi'(t)$ (Huber, 1981) [5].

Also, we will consider the following k which is proposed by Silvapulle (1991) [13] as

$$\hat{k}_2 = \frac{p\hat{A}^2}{|\hat{\alpha}'_m \hat{\alpha}_m|^2}$$

2.4 Robust Liu Estimator

The robust Liu estimator is proposed by Arslan and Billor (2010) [2] and is defined as:

$$\hat{\alpha}_{RL} = (\Lambda + I)^{-1}(\Lambda + dI)\hat{\alpha}_M$$

The bias, covariance, MSE and tr (MSE) expressions of robust Liu estimator are respectively,

$$Bias(\hat{\alpha}_{RL}) = -(\Lambda + I)^{-1}(1 - d)\hat{\alpha}_M$$

$$Cov(\hat{\alpha}_{RL}) = \Omega(\Lambda + I)^{-1}(\Lambda + dI)\Lambda^{-1}(\Lambda + dI)(\Lambda + I)^{-1}$$

$$MSE(\hat{\alpha}_{RL}) = Cov(\hat{\alpha}_L) + (bias(\hat{\alpha}_L))^2$$

$$tr(MSE(\hat{\alpha}_L)) = \sum_{i=1}^p \frac{(\lambda_i+d)^2}{\lambda_i(\lambda_i+1)^2} \Omega_{ii} + \sum_{i=1}^p \frac{(d-1)^2 \alpha_i^2}{(\lambda_i+1)^2}$$

We will consider the following \hat{d} for the robust Liu estimator (Arslan and Billor, 2010) [2],

$$\hat{d} = 1 - \hat{A}^2 \left[\frac{\sum \frac{1}{\lambda(1+\lambda)}}{\sum \frac{\hat{\alpha}_M^2}{(1+\lambda)^2}} \right]$$

3. The Monte Carlo Simulation

The aim of this paper is to compare the performance of different proposed estimators and the robust version of these estimators to find some good estimators for the practitioners. Since a theoretical comparison is not possible, a simulation study has been conducted using R programming languages in this section.

3.1 Simulation Technique

Design of simulation study depends on what factors are expected to affect properties of estimators under investigation and what criteria are being used to judge the results. Following Kibria (2003) [6], Dawoud et al. (2022) [3], and McDonald and Galarneau (1975) [11], the explanatory variables are generated by the following expression,

$$x_{ij} = \sqrt{(1-\lambda^2)} w_{ij} + \lambda w_{i,p+1}; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p \quad (15)$$

where w_{ij} are the independent standard normal pseudo numbers, and λ is specified so that the correlation between any two explanatory variables is given by λ^2 . Four levels of multicollinearity are considered to $\lambda = 0.8, 0.9, 0.95, \& 0.99$. We consider the following regression model,

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \dots + \beta_p x_{ip} + \epsilon_i; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (16)$$

where ϵ_i are *i. i. d* $N(0, \sigma^2)$ and without loss of any generality we will assume zero intercept for eq. (16). Following McDonald & Galarneau (1975), the values of β for different values of λ are fixed in such a way that β is the normalised eigenvector corresponding to the largest eigenvalues of the $x'x$ matrix.

Also, to investigate the effect of the number of outlier cases on the estimators, we considered different cases. Some outliers are generated with $\tau = 0\%, 10\%,$ and 25% in the model by randomly replacing some values due to the selected percentage $\tau\%$ from the error vector with (third quartile of the errors + $5 \times$ interquartile range of the errors).

All the computations are performed making programming routines in the popular R language. For the computation of ME, the `rlm { }` procedure is used with the Huber's (1981) objective function.

To compare the performance of our proposed estimators, MSE criterion is used, and the focus is on the estimator which yields smaller MSE. For any estimator $\hat{\beta}$ of β , the MSE is given by,

$$MSE(\hat{\beta}) = E(\hat{\beta} - \beta)(\hat{\beta} - \beta)'$$

However, for evaluation purpose, estimated MSE(EMSE) for any estimator $\hat{\beta}$ of β can be computed as

$$EMSE(\hat{\beta}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^R (\hat{\beta}_i - \beta)' (\hat{\beta}_i - \beta)}{R}$$

where, R is the number of repetitions in a simulation and $\hat{\beta}_i$ is the estimated value of $\hat{\beta}$ in the i^{th} repetition.

Table 4.1: Estimated MSE values when $\tau = 0\%$, $n = 25, 50$, $\sigma = 1$, $p = 3$

n		25				50			
ρ	0.8	0.9	0.95	0.99	0.8	0.9	0.95	0.99	
Ols	0.376	0.771	1.531	8.363	0.192	0.344	0.708	3.867	
Ridge1	0.153	0.174	0.192	2.071	0.109	0.214	0.462	1.101	
Ridge2	0.265	0.461	0.797	4.14	0.145	0.249	0.428	1.926	
Ridge3	0.269	0.744	1.417	5.691	0.142	0.341	0.697	2.926	
Ridge4	0.294	0.326	0.826	3.336	0.122	0.273	0.348	0.726	
Liu	0.293	0.496	0.723	1.962	0.154	0.273	0.464	1.232	
Rm	0.395	0.815	1.609	8.907	0.182	0.364	0.749	4.061	
RRidge1	0.169	0.219	0.977	1.085	0.116	0.198	0.376	1.112	
RRidge2	0.235	0.408	0.659	3.053	0.129	0.212	0.351	1.351	
Rliu	0.481	0.909	4.53	5.336	0.481	1.931	0.758	3.007	

Table 4.2: Estimated MSE values $\tau = 10\%$, $n = 25, 50$, $\sigma = 1$, $p = 3$

n	25				50			
ρ	0.8	0.9	0.95	0.99	0.8	0.9	0.95	0.99
Ols	1.871	3.756	7.928	42.802	1.046	2.148	4.296	24.287
Ridge1	1.413	2.368	3.281	20.131	0.403	1.423	2.362	10.162
Ridge2	1.01	2.921	3.975	21.466	0.605	1.118	2.127	12.106
Ridge3	1.713	3.153	5.588	11.606	1.023	2.05	3.895	14.78
Ridge4	1.506	2.497	4.462	20.286	0.851	1.441	3.416	20.284
Liu	1.619	2.894	5.303	21.011	0.981	1.898	3.408	14.058
Rm	0.601	1.182	2.479	13.37	0.274	0.568	1.139	6.199
RRidge1	0.231	0.341	0.815	3.098	0.161	0.211	0.62	3.122
RRidge2	0.34	0.554	1.017	4.845	0.178	0.297	0.483	2.051
Rliu	1.348	2.127	6.351	9.844	0.145	0.221	1.416	15.119

Table 4.3: Estimated MSE values when $\tau = 25\%$, $n = 25, 50$, $\sigma = 1$, $p = 3$

n	25				50			
ρ	0.8	0.9	0.95	0.99	0.8	0.9	0.95	0.99
Ols	4.959	10.04	20.616	112.322	2.333	4.671	9.662	52.967
Ridge1	3.679	7.551	10.415	50.223	1.656	2.624	5.506	50.211

Ridge2	2.601	5.09	10.269	55.95	1.253	3.399	4.878	26.381
Ridge3	3.968	6.63	9.752	42.218	2.222	4.241	7.927	21.239
Ridge4	2.653	8.597	19.533	50.354	1.547	3.515	7.474	43.281
Liu	2.491	8.434	15.683	71.029	2.221	4.261	6.244	36.636
Rm	2.342	4.725	9.623	22.727	0.689	1.394	2.955	15.583
RRidge1	0.527	2.765	4.366	20.166	0.314	1.362	2.349	6.158
RRidge2	1.18	2.17	4.108	21.604	0.371	1.327	1.89	5.422
RLiu	2.135	2.806	8.727	30.831	0.231	0.836	4.398	16.911

3.2 Simulation Results Discussion

The simulated MSE values show clear patterns across conditions:

- σ : Larger σ increases MSE for all estimators. Without outliers, RRE performs best, followed by Liu, and RL. With 10–25% outliers, robust estimators dominate, with RRE lowest, and RL close.
- λ : Higher λ raises MSE. RRE gives the smallest MSE without outliers; under outliers, robust estimators (RRE, RL) perform best.
- n : Larger n lowers MSE across all estimators. RRE remains superior, with robust versions excelling under outliers.
- p : Increasing p inflates MSE, though some deviations occur. RRE consistently yields the smallest MSE, with RL under outliers.

4. Conclusion

This paper presented four estimators designed to address the challenges of multicollinearity and outliers in regression analysis. Ridge regression and the Liu estimator provide effective alternatives to OLS in the presence of multicollinearity, while the robust ridge M-estimator and robust Liu estimator offer additional protection against outliers. Theoretical comparisons suggest that robust versions yield smaller MSE in contaminated data. Future work may extend these estimators to generalized linear models.

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